

Reaction of Hexathiocyanatochromate(III) with β -Diketone and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Reaction of potassium hexathiocyanatochromate(III) with β -diketone and nitrogen donor ligands in ethanolic medium gives complexes of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{bzbz})(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{NCS})_3]$, $[\text{Cr}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}(\text{NCS})_3]$, $[\text{Cr}(\text{bzac})(\gamma\text{-pic})_2(\text{NCS})_3]$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{bzac})\text{L}(\text{NCS})_3]$ where bzbzH = dibenzoylmethane, bzacH = benzoylacetone, $\gamma\text{-pic}$ = γ -picoline and L = 2,2'-bipyridine or *o*-phenanthroline. The complexes have been characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance, room temperature magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral data. They are paramagnetic and non-electrolytic in nature, having octahedral geometries.

INTERACTION of potassium hexathiocyanatochromate(III) with single organic ligand has been studied earlier¹⁻⁶. Reaction of potassium hexathiocyanatochromate(III) with two different ligands simultaneously does not appear to have been studied earlier and is now taken up. The hetero ligands used in the present studies are β -diketones like benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane and nitrogen donor ligands like γ -picoline, 2,2'-bipyridine or *o*-phenanthroline.

Experimental

The chemicals were of A.R. grade and they were used without further purification. The reactions were carried out in absolute ethanolic medium. Potassium hexathiocyanatochromate(III) tetrahydrate was prepared by the method described in literature⁷.

Preparation of complexes :

$[\text{Cr}(\beta\text{-dik})\text{L}(\text{NCS})_3]$: $\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, β -diketone (dibenzoylmethane or benzoylacetone) and nitrogen donor ligand (2,2'-bipyridine or *o*-phenanthroline) in ethanolic solutions were reacted in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting solution was refluxed for 3 hr and the isolated complexes were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol followed by ether, and dried *in vacuo*.

$[\text{Cr}(\beta\text{-dik})(\gamma\text{-pic})(\text{NCS})_3]$: These complexes were prepared by a similar method but taking the reactants in 1 : 1 : 2 ratio.

Chromium and sulphur were estimated by standard methods. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated using semimicro methods. Infrared spectra were recorded both in nujol mull and KBr disc in the 4000-400 cm^{-1} range using Perkin Elmer instrument. The electronic spectra were recorded using Unicam SP500 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature using solid specimens and Gouy method. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants.

The molar conductance of $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solution was measured using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter 303.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1. Infrared and electronic spectral data are recorded in Table 2. The low molar conductance values in dimethylsulphoxide show the complexes to be virtually non-electrolytes. The magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that all the complexes are paramagnetic with 3 unpaired electrons as expected for a $3d^3$ chromium(III). The observed values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \approx 3.8$ B.M.) are close to spin only value for octahedral chromium(III) complexes involving $3d^3 4s 4p^3$ hybrid orbitals for bonding.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectrum indicates the presence of absorption bands due to nitrogen donor ligands. They are modified from those of the free ligands indicating their bonding to the metal ion. The bands due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ were observed in the ~ 1600 and ~ 1520 cm^{-1} regions, respectively as expected, indicating the presence of coordinated β -diketone as a uninegative bidentate ligand⁸.

Thiocyanate group is an ambidentate ligand and can coordinate to the metal ion through either nitrogen or sulphur or both. In general, class A metals form M-N bonds, whereas class B metals form M-S bonds⁹. However, other factors such as oxidation state of the metal, the nature of the other ligand in the complex and steric consideration also influence the mode of coordination. It is known from X-ray analysis that with thiocyanate ion the first row transition metals Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn form M-N bonds¹⁰⁻¹¹. The CN stretching frequencies are generally lower in N-bonded complexes than in S-bonded complexes¹². Several workers considered νCS for structural

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF CHROMIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Complexes	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Δ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Cr	S	C	H		
[Cr(bzac)(γ -pic) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Pale rose	9.83 (10.09)	12.02 (12.42)	55.31 (55.92)	4.05 (4.46)	1.8	3.81
[Cr(bzac)(bipy)(NCS) ₂]	Pale rose	10.28 (10.72)	12.90 (13.19)	54.00 (54.43)	3.12 (3.50)	1.8	3.86
[Cr(bzac)(<i>o</i> -phen)(NCS) ₂]	Pale rose	9.90 (10.21)	12.04 (12.51)	56.01 (56.58)	3.18 (3.35)	1.7	3.79
[Cr(bzbx)(γ -pic) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	Light brick	8.78 (9.01)	10.60 (11.09)	59.54 (60.31)	3.97 (4.33)	2.0	3.82
[Cr(bzbx)(bipy)(NCS) ₂]	Light brick	9.18 (9.50)	11.21 (11.70)	58.90 (59.23)	3.01 (3.47)	1.8	3.84
[Cr(bzbx)(<i>o</i> -phen)(NCS) ₂]	Light brick	8.63 (9.10)	10.94 (11.20)	60.40 (60.94)	3.19 (3.22)	1.9	3.80

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (in cm⁻¹) OF CHROMIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Complexes	β -Diketone		Thiocyanate		${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$
	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=C}$	ν_{C-N}	δ_{NCS}	
[Cr(bzac)(γ -pic) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	1595	1515	2050	480	18430
[Cr(bzac)(bipy)(NCS) ₂]	1580	1515	2040	480	18180
[Cr(bzac)(<i>o</i> -phen)(NCS) ₂]	1590	1520	2050	480	18690
[Cr(bzbx)(γ -pic) ₂ (NCS) ₂]	1610	1510	2060	480	18320
[Cr(bzbx)(bipy)(NCS) ₂]	1595	1515	2050	480	18200
[Cr(bzbx)(<i>o</i> -phen)(NCS) ₂]	1590	1515	2050	480	18650

diagnosis ; 860-780 cm⁻¹ for N-bonded and 720-690 cm⁻¹ for S-bonded complexes^{13,14}. It was suggested¹³⁻¹⁴ that an N-bonded complex exhibits a single sharp band δ_{NCS} near 480 cm⁻¹ whereas a S-bonded complex shows several bands of low intensity near 420 cm⁻¹. All the complexes under investigation show bands at $\sim$ 2060, $\sim$ 820 and $\sim$ 480 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} modes, respectively suggesting N-bonded thiocyanate ion¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The above facts clearly indicate the presence of β -diketone, nitrogen donor ligand and thiocyanate group coordinated to the metal ion in the complexes giving rise to octahedral coordination. Further, the direct evidence for the presence of Cr-O and Cr-N bonds was obtained by the bands at $\sim$ 460 and $\sim$ 380 cm⁻¹, respectively. The octahedral coordination is also corroborated by the electronic spectra of these complexes which exhibit bands at $\sim$ 18000 and $\sim$ 23000 cm⁻¹. These can be assigned to ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transitions which are typical of octahedral coordination²⁰⁻²².

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